

Library Management and Information Systems of Non Government University Libraries in Bangladesh

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Abstract

Private Universities are not new dimension in the Bangladeshi concept. The concepts are very much establish and provided quality education. Libraries are the essential elements to provide quality education. This study took an initiative to study the management and information systems of private university libraries on the basis of experience, observation and group study of the library professional. The study found that maximum libraries of the private universities are provided quality services to its users and establish good management systems.

Keywords: publications, libraries, universities, Bangladesh, cataloging, online database services, journal repositories, quality education, indexing and Abstracting Services, etc.

1. Introduction

A university library is a part of a university organization which aims at the advancement of the functions of its parent body [1]. Kumar (2006) [2] asserts that a university is supposed to perform the following functions: 1.Teaching, 2.Research, 3.Publications, 4.Conservation of knowledge and ideas, 5.Extension services. The library supports the reading and research needs of its users for that particular institution. It is the library's responsibility to provide better services to its clients to make sure that information sources, services and resources are well utilized for users' benefits. Hence user education program is very crucial for library user's achievements [3].

University library is an integrated part of any university. Its aim is to serve the actual need of its students, teachers and others officials by providing their desired information such as books and non-book materials. The libraries are also dedicated to promote higher education and research. The effective and efficient services depend on the nature of management and existing information systems.

2. Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to analyze the status of library management and information systems of non government universities in Bangladesh. The specific objectives are as follows:

- a. To find out provided library services to the users
- b. To observe the status of library management
- c. To identify problems faced by the users of the respective library
- d. To provide recommendations for improving library systems and services

3. Literature Review

Academic libraries are attached to tertiary institutions such as universities, polytechnic institutions, colleges of education, colleges of agriculture, colleges of technology and also research institutes [4]. Singh and Kaur (2009) [5] stressed that preservation and access to knowledge and information is the main mandate of academic libraries alongside supporting the mission of their parent institutions which is teaching and research. Haliso (2010) observed that academic libraries are institutions that are established to take care of the information need of students, lecturers, researchers and other community of scholars. Their mission is providing quality information service and knowledge products (print and electronic) to resident community of scholars. In 2008, there were 1,64,624 students studying in public universities (excluding National University and Open University) and 1,82,641 students were studying in Private Universities [6].

4. Research Methodology

This research conducted on the basis of experience, observation and group study of the library professional. The study mainly used primary and secondary data. Primary data have been collected by interview of the different types of users of the library such as faculty members (Professor, Associate Professor, Assistant Professor and Lecturer), students (Graduates and Post Graduates), library professionals, administrator and researchers.

Review of literature, journal articles and other relevant documents and books are also used for the sources of secondary information.

5. Non Government University in Bangladesh: An overview

Non-government universities in Bangladesh which is commonly known as Private Universities are those higher educational institutions which are established privately by a group of people or organizations with the permission of the Government aimed to spreading the opportunities of higher education among larger number of students under Private University Act, 1992 (Amended 1998) that was passed on 9th August in 1992.

According to the Act 'Private University' means; any private university established under this Act; and following the provisions of this act and in fulfillment of the conditions provided by the government, any institution managed under the affiliation of any foreign university which is operating courses of Honors or Masters Degree, Diploma or Certificate Courses or any institution which is offering Degree, Diploma or Certificates (Section-2, Sub-section-(g), Private University Act, 1992, Amended 1998 and 2010).

A good number of public universities are providing higher education, but it is not sufficient to cope with the need and demand of the society and the public universities in Bangladesh would not be able to meet the increasing demand for higher education.

A remarkable number of students have been depriving from the opportunities to complete their higher education from public universities. As a result a significant number of students are also going abroad to achieve higher education. To consider above mentioned situations, Bangladesh government took a decision of introducing private university. The provision of private university Act had been introduced through Private University Act 1992 duly amended in 1998 and 2010. With the passage of time the population of Bangladesh has been growing faster. Consequently the students at university have also been growing enormously and the inadequate number of public universities cannot keep pace with increasing amount of students for higher education. To bridge up this gap the Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh passed the "Private University Act" in 1992; where a person or a group of persons, Foundation, Trust etc were allowed to set up and run a private university. Accordingly the private universities have been established as a non profitable organization. Usually a private university provides limited scope to students compared to public universities.

With the expansion of education facilities in secondary and higher secondary level the demand for higher education has increased dramatically in the recent years. The public higher institutions were not successfully meeting this pressure. To meet the demand and reduce the increasing cost at the higher level, government opened the opportunity for private sector participation in higher education. As a result, the number of students in the private universities is increasing day by day. The private universities in Bangladesh recorded a phenomenal growth after the enactment of the Private University Act in 1992. Both public and private sector's institutions are providing higher education. Higher education in Bangladesh is provided by different type of agencies. There are certain patterns in the ownership of private universities. First, most agencies are non-profit entities. In most cases, a group of like-minded philanthropic and relatively resourceful people were organized to establish a university. Their intention is to satisfy the existing excess demand for some types of university courses/degrees in the country. Leadership in founding this breed of universities has originated mainly from the visionary elites, e.g. highly placed (former) civil servants, industrialists, businessmen and professionals. Some universities highlighted religious-oriented course. These types of institutions teach Islamic ideology-based courses in addition to market-oriented courses. Some universities are established by country's leading NGO.

Renowned NGO, Association of Social Advancement (ASA) established ASA University, another leading NGO Bangladesh Rural Advancement Committee (BRAC) established BRAC University and Gonoshastho established Gono Bishyabidyalyo. Out of these types of founders, Chittagong City Corporation (CCC) established a University in Chittagong named Premier University.

The University Grants Commission (UGC) of Bangladesh is the statutory apex body in the field of higher education in Bangladesh. The primary objectives of the UGC are to supervise, maintain, promote and coordinate university education. It is also responsible for maintaining standard and quality in all the public and private universities in Bangladesh. The UGC assesses the needs of the public universities in terms of funding and advice Government in various issues related to higher education in Bangladesh. UGC of Bangladesh was established under the President's Order (P.O.) No. 10 of 1973 which was deemed to have come into force with effect from 16 December 1972. Though, University Grand Commission (UGC) is the only formal regulatory body of the country's higher education.

The universities in Bangladesh are mainly categorized into public and private universities. The public universities are autonomous and funded by the government, whereas, private universities are funded by non-government organizations and private bodies. At present, there are 34 public and 76 private universities in Bangladesh (University Grants Commission Website, last visited on November 11, 2013).

6. Different Sections of the library

It is a known fact that the responsibilities of library are collecting, organizing, interpreting and disseminating information. The private university library is divided mainly in the following sections.

a. Library Management and Administration

Library management and administration is of the parts of library section and usually performed by the librarian or his/ her nominated officer. Preparing library budget, training and supervising the staff, planning library development, creating library rules and regulations, supervising acquisition policies, maintaining library committee, preparing library report, maintaining personal records are the main activities of library management and administration.

b. Circulation Section

Circulation section is a very important section in the library. All the library resources are borrowed by the users with this section. Records of borrowed materials are preserved properly. Thus lending and borrowing of books in library is known as circulation. Library members, library collections, efficiency of library staff, location of the library building and opening hours of the library are very important to encourage the circulation section.

c. Procurement Section

The procurement section of the university library procures new materials to add to the exiting collections to meet the requirement of the users and readers. It also fulfills the university's research purpose.

d. Reading Room Section

Reading room is a section where the readers and users keep their mind for reading the borrowed materials from the library. Sufficient chair and table are arranged in this section. The reader returns the books to the shelves after uses.

e. Acquisition Section

Receiving requests from Heads of the Departments for new books, duplicate checking, ordering, accessioning of books and processing bills for payment are the main functions of this section. Suggestions and recommendations for the purchase of new books can be submitted to this section. All the books received from vendors/publishers and the donated books are physically processed and accessioned in this section. The section also has the responsibility of scrutinizing and passing bill for books received.

f. Classification Section

Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) scheme is used for classifying books according to the subject. Each book is assigned a Call Number which consists of a class number and Book Number. Class Number is assigned to a book according to its subject matter. Book Number individualizes a book among others having the same Class Number. The Call Number is written on the spine label of the book. Library of Congress Classification also used for this purpose.

g. Catalogue Section

The bibliographic details like edition, year of publication, subject, keywords, etc. are prepared by this section. The details entered in this section are indexed on various fields like Author, Title, Subjects, Classification Number, Keywords, etc.

h. Periodicals Section

Both Bangladeshi and Foreign journals currently subscribed, and journals received as gift are displayed in shelves in this section. News-papers and popular magazines are also available for reading. A journal, on completion of its volume will be processed for binding. After the binding is over, the volume will be accessioned.

i. Information Technology Section

Automated and Digital Library Services are provided from this section. All sections of the Library have been connected through LAN. Computer Data Base of the holdings of the Library has already been created using the Library Management Software. Maintaining Hardware and Software, Providing Internet Service, E-resources Access Services, Remote Login Service, Document Delivery Service, maintaining library databases, generating Bar-coded, Barcode Labels for books, Spine Labels for books, Creating Membership Details are some of the activities of the I.T. section.

j. Reference Section

This section has a good reference collection consisting of various encyclopaedias, dictionaries, year books, almanacs, atlases, biographies, etc. of the national and international coverage and other reference books.

k. Stack Section

This is the most important section of the Library. Its function is the display and maintenance of books which are issued on loan. Books are arranged on shelves according to call Number.

l. U.N. Depository Section/ Language Section

Publications of the United Nations are received by the University Library and arranged in this section according to the subject. The documents are available for reference only. It also preserves the books of different language of the world.

m. Theses/Dissertation Section

Ph.D. Theses, M. Phil. and MSS Dissertations of the University and others are received and maintained by this section. The bibliographic details of the Theses and Dissertations are available on OPAC. The required Theses/Dissertations could be searched through OPAC and referred.

n. Reprographic Section

A photocopying machine are introduced in the library to reproduce quickly and conveniently perfect copies of parts of books, periodical articles, and documents and records for the library users and readers.

o. Binding Section

Library materials would be damaged which are frequently used. Besides that, some careless readers, bookworms and insects and some other factors like excessive heat, humidity, dust and light are also dormant enemies of books. They damage and harm them. For this purpose, repair of damaged books and periodicals and their binding is associated with the library. A binding section should be introduced in the library for uniform binding of the materials, cheaper from the commercial binder, minor repairing of books can be done quickly also better and quick services are available.

p. Audio- visual Section

Audio-visual section is an important and modern service oriented section in the private university libraries. This section includes CD, VCD, cassettes, electronic books & reference materials etc.

7. Library Resources

Library resources especially reading materials are the main and essential component in the library. The effectiveness of the library and the level of satisfaction of the users are fully depending on the library resources. The following library resources are found in the private university libraries.

a. Books, b. Reference Sources; such as dictionaries, encyclopedias, directories, bibliographical reference sources, handbooks and manuals, almanacs, yearbooks, maps and atlases, c. Government Document, d. Media resources, e. newspapers, f. Journals, g. Magazines, h. Dissertation and theses, i. students final year projects, j. Manuscripts and Rare books, and k. Audio- Visual Materials.

8. Private University Library Systems

System is structures which are follow by the respected user or responded. A common library system of the private university libraries in Bangladesh are described in the bellow.

a. Hours of Services

The library hours of the maximum universities are 9:00 am to 9:00 pm from Sunday to Thursday. Friday, Saturday, other public holiday and other dates announced by the University authorities are closed. The libraries are also open on holidays for special academic programs.

b. Users of the library

User is a focal point of all libraries and the primary objectives of libraries are to satisfy its users. Students, faculties, researchers, officers, research assistants and faculty assistants are the users of the private university libraries.

c. Library Personnel

The persons who are worked in the library are known as library personnel. There are two types of library personnel in the library, such as i. Professional personnel: the people who are achieved any professional degree on information science and library management (ISLM) is called professional personnel and ii. Non-professional personnel: the persons who are not achieved any professional degree.

d. Academic and Professional Qualifications of the library Personnel

The personnel who are engaged in the private university libraries maximum are academic qualified and professionally experienced.

e. Status of the library personnel

The Librarian of the private university library holds the rank of full professor as an academic staff. The other officers of the library that is Deputy Librarian, Assistant Librarian, and Junior Assistant Librarian are also hold the rank of Associate professor, Assistant professor and Lecturer respectively. It is also true that maximum private university do not follow the structure in the initial stages of the university.

f. Library Committee

The library committee is a body to form for purpose of maintenance and development of the library and decision making at policy level. In the private university library, librarian is the executive responsibility for the day to day management of the library, where as over policy is controlled by the university through the library committee. Librarian acts as member-secretary in the library committee.

g. Classification System Used

Classification is the major work in the library and the place of the books in the library determine according to its classification number or call number. Although there are many classification schemes in the world, major private university libraries in Bangladesh are using Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) which is developed by Melvil Dewey. Library of Congress Classification (LC) is also followed a few of university libraries.

h. Cataloguing Code Adopted

Library catalogue is the mirror of the library. Library catalogue is a list of bibliographical information of the library materials which follow a systematic rule. Most of the private university libraries are following AACR-2 to prepare a catalogue card.

i. Source of Finance

Finance is a vital component for a well establish university library. Tuition fees of the students of the university are the main source of finance of the private university libraries. Besides grants allocated from the university budget; grants from the UGC, endowments and gifts and miscellaneous are also sources of finance.

j. Purchase Method

Maximum private universities of Bangladesh are followed the appropriate government rules and regulations for purchasing all library resources from home and abroad.

k. Training

A few of private university libraries offers training program for those who are interested to know how to use the library and others information technology in higher education and research, and how to search information from digital libraries. These training programs are mainly designed for the students and faculties so that they can easily get their desired information easily.

l. Library Rules and Regulations

Library committee of the university prepares a set of rules and regulation to control the library properly. Library hours, readers facilities, lending facilities of the

library resources, common rules to use the library, overdue policy, membership procedures are included in the library rules and regulations.

9. Private University Library Services

Library services present a picture and play an important role to its user's community. Private university libraries are provided the following services and facilities to the users.

a. Reference Services

A few of private university libraries have been providing references to its users as a wide range and maximum universities are providing as a limited range. The university libraries are provided reference services as a central reference department in a general library building, reference department with divisional library and providing personalized services to readers.

b. Reading room services

Reading rooms with a good environment, fine architecture, sound proof, controlled temperature, well ventilation, proper lighting are provided by maximum university libraries. The reading materials of the reading rooms are arranged in open access. As a result the users can read their books and others reading materials without any hesitation and difficulties.

c. Circulation Services

Circulation services are very important service for the library. Lending and borrowing services, users' guidance, reference services, referral services, in-house telephonic response and any query regarding library services are maintained by circulation section.

d. Current Awareness Service (CAS)

Current awareness services provided recent information and recent developments of the particular users' interest to the respective users. This service is very important for the advanced level users.

e. Selective Dissemination of Information (SDI) Services

Selective dissemination of information is a very popular service in the university libraries. This is a system of determining the fields of interest of clients, sometimes called interest profiles, then notifying clients of new data that would match their profiles.

f. Bibliographical Services

To enhance the utilization of library resources private university library compiles bibliographies on specific subject such as marketing, business law, pharmacy, management, finance, English etc.

g. Photocopy Services

Photocopy or reprographic services are very important for the users and the private university libraries are providing this service with pay for each copy.

h. Indexing and Abstracting Services

Maximum private university libraries do not provide traditional indexing and abstracting services. A few of libraries purchase the prepared index and abstract for the users on their required subject.

i. Information Services (News Paper Clipping Service)

An information services or on-demand information retrieval services are available a good numbers of private university libraries. For this purpose the library maintains the news papper clipping activities. The libraries also provide indexing and current contents services which includes the copy of the content pages of the periodicals received in the last couple of weeks.

j. Internet and E-mail Services

Maximum private university libraries provide internet and e-mail services to its users as a modern library.

k. Library Online Database

A good number of private university library have been providing online database services to its users. It subscribes to leading online journal such as IEEE (The institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers), ACM (Association for Computing Machinery), HINARI (Health Inter Network Access to Research Initiative), AGORA (Access to Global Online Research in Agriculture), OUP (Oxford University Press), High wire Press journals etc for its users.

l. In-House Computerized Catalogue

In-house computerized catalogue are introduced a good number of private university libraries. The users of this library are able to search library catalogue with his/her computer from any place of this campus through internet.

m. Internet Searching

The Internet is a massive resource of information to which anyone can connect and from which anyone can receive data. To provide faster and up-to-date data maximum private university have been providing internet services to its users.

n. Union Catalogue

A few private university libraries have been linked with a web based union catalogue through the Sustainable Development Network Programme (SDNP) - a project of UNDP.

o. Book Display Programme

Book display programme is one of the most important services of private university library. A good number of private university libraries has been introducing book display programme for its users and readers.

p. Training

A private university library offers a certificate course titled 'Certificate Course in Digital & Online Librarianship' for those who are interested to know how to use the internet resources in higher education and research, and how to design and maintain website, and set up online digital libraries.

q. Audio-visual services

Audio-visual materials are very essential and modern equipment for a library. A separate section for audio-visual materials is available in the maximum private university libraries of Dhaka city. Collection of materials, processing, preserving and disseminate are the major activities of this section.

r. Users' Orientation

The main purpose of the users' orientation program of a library is to familiar the library resources to the users and readers. However, it also presents how to use the library properly, accurately and effectively, lending procedures, membership process etc in the program.

10. Automation Activities of the Private University Libraries

Automation is the technique, a process or a system, which operate automatically. According to the Encyclopaedia of Library and Information Science (1990) automation is the technology concerned with a design and development of the process and systems that minimizes the necessity of human intervention in their operation.

There are a few of private university library in Bangladesh that are fully automated and most of the libraries are in the initial stages of the automation activities. Self developed and customized software are used for automation purposes. KOHA is the open sources software which is popularly used in the private university libraries to create automation, CDS/ISIS software developed by UNESCO, GLAS (Graphical Library Automation System), Alice for Windows are also used. Dspace and Green Stone Digital library software are widely used to create digital library. Acquisition, classification, cataloguing, circulation, serial control, access right to staff members, access right to library users, preparing library report, information retrieval, online public access catalogue, searching library database, current awareness service (CAS), selective dissemination of information services (SDI), indexing and abstracting services, resources sharing and library networking activities have been completed successfully with the automation. Well-trained and skilled manpower, strong network, sufficient budget, the complexity of university administration are the main problems for library automation in our country. With automation the following activities have been done section wise.

a. Automated Acquisition Section

Acquisition section is responsible for the acquisition of all book and non-book reading materials by purchase, gift and exchange. It also maintains exchange relation with libraries and other learnt organization of home and abroad. Ordering, duplicate checking, cancellation of orders, receipt processing, payment, fund accounting, vendor maintain and accounting, currency control, compilation of report etc have been complied automatically in the private university libraries.

b. Automated Circulation Section

Registration of the library members, charging and discharging of documents, updating the records, preparation of remainders, information retrieval, generate barcode of the library resources, calculation of fine, report preparation, inter library loan etc activities have been done in the automated circulation section of a library.

c. Automated Processing Section

Accessioning, classifying, serial control and cataloguing of library materials are completed in this section. The automated processing sections of a library are managed and controlled entire activities involved in a processing section.

Books are classified according to standard classification schedule with the help of web publication. Accession register are maintained by electronically with a database. Catalogues is prepared and submit on the internet with the help of computer and online catalogue are available. The automated processing section of a library also establishes an automated serials control system.

d. Automated Reference Section

The reference section of a library contains contemporary reference materials as well as journals, periodicals, newspapers, and magazine etc. In the automated reference section keep the all the record of this section electronically with in a file.

e. Cyber and AVM Section

Internet services, CD writing, downloading and printing services, copying of important document etc services have been provided from this section and all the services are provided automatically.

f. Automated Serial Control

Input essential data, prepare order list of new serials, mode of payment, receipt and updating the records, receipt to vendors and publishers, preparing the list of present collections, additions, missing, cancelled serials chronologically, renewal and cancellation of present subscriptions, sending reminders and follow-up of missing issues, binding control, accession register of bound serials, prepare budget etc activities are done in a automated section of a library.

g. Automated Documentation Section

The automated documentation section of a library have been completed the following activities, such as indexing and abstracting of micro and macro documents, thesaurus construction, compilation of union catalogue, bibliographic control, current awareness services, literature search, selective dissemination of information, news paper clipping etc.

h. Automated Information Retrieval

Collecting information and retrieval is an important activity for a library. The following activities are done with automated information retrieval system, such as database creation and maintenance, interactive searching, saving of in house as well as external databases, search and print of specified requirement etc.

i. Communication networks

Library Cooperation (cooperative acquisition, cataloguing and coordinated information services, resources sharing), Access to Database (information services, back-up service document delivery), CD-ROM Services (information searching, text delivery), Online Search (access to database, downloading, E-mail (electronic mailbox, bulletin boards) etc activities are completed in a automated communication system.

11. Online Resources Section/Digital Library Services of Private University Libraries

A good number of private university libraries are subscribed world wide online databases to meet the increasing demand of their users. The following databases are very important and necessary.

a. HINARI: Heath Inter Network Access to Research Initiatives (HINARI) provides a vast library of the latest and best information on public health with more than 3200 scientific publications. The web collection is available through the efforts of World Health Organization (WHO) together with the 6 biggest biomedical publishers: Blackwell, Elsevier Science, the Harcourt Worldwide STM Group, Wolters Kluwer International Health and Science, Springer Verlag and John Wiley.

b. AGORA: AGORA provides a collection of 849 journals to institutions in 69 countries, set by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations (UN) together with major publishers in the fields of food, agriculture, environmental science and related social sciences.

c. JSTOR: The private university libraries also provide the JSTOR digital library services for its users. The JSTOR archive holds the complete digitized back runs of core scholarly journals, starting with the very first issues and new titles and disciplines are being added regularly. Full-text articles may be printed or downloaded in Adobe files for use.

d. DOAJ: Full text, quality controlled scientific and scholarly journals are included in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ). More than 700 journals are searchable at articles level. Articles may be searched by title, author and subject or through journal tables of contents and the users are capable to read, download and distribute from the directory.

e. ACM: Association of Computing Machinery (ACM) is a one kind of digital library included journals which all are in print version and soft copy, magazines, newsletters for downloading, uploading and printing. Everyone can access in this library but the students of Computer Science and Engineering department are getting more benefit from these services.

f. IEEE: International Engineering of Electrical and Electronics (IEEE) is a digital library including journals, magazines, newsletters for downloading, uploading and for printing. The subscriber users can search by author, title or keywords.

g. OUP (Oxford University Press) and High Wire Press: The online database of Oxford University Press (OUP) is also used by the Bangladeshi private university library users frequently.

12. Consortium

A good number of private university libraries have been subscribed to the 'Bangladesh INASP-PERii Consortium (BIPC)'. Using this consortium the users are able to access full- text articles, abstracts and bibliographical information of online journals of different publishers on different disciplines. Bangladesh Academy of Science (BAS) is the focal point of this consortium.

13. Database Management Systems and Use of Digital Resources

Traditional library system in our country is laborious and time consuming. So to reduce these problems and to save the valuable time of the library reader and user's database management and uses of electronic resources have been introduced in the private university libraries. Most of the users of the Library are using the On-line Public Access Catalogue to find the holdings of the University Library. The following databases are available on online public access catalogue (OPAC) book database, serial database, theses database, report database etc.

14. Marketing Polices of the Private University Libraries

Librarians and information specialists have debated the ideas of marketing for the information sector. There is a new meaning of marketing in library and information centers. Jesti and Parameswari (2002) [7] express that libraries and information centers have begun to realize that marketing of information products and services is an integral part of administration, especially as a means for improving user satisfaction and promoting the use of services by current and potential users.

Marketing aims to identify the client base, and to determine and fill its needs, wants, and demands by designing and delivering appropriate products and services. The main focus of the concept is the client, and the goal is client satisfaction [8]. Rowley (2001) stated that marketing is the management process which identifies, anticipates, and supplies customer requirements efficiently and profitably. Kotler (1999) [9] defined that marketing is the process of planning and executing the conception, pricing, promotion and distribution of goods, services and ideas to create exchanges with target groups that satisfy customers and organizational objectives.

By the term marketing, we study concepts like building customer relationships, branding and corporate identity, marketing communications, price and pricing policy, collecting marketing data and marketing strategy and planning. There is a new meaning of marketing in library and information sector. There is still considerable misunderstanding in most of the library and information sector as to what constitutes effective marketing. To some, it is still primarily equated with selling and the pursuit of sales, rather than customer satisfaction [10].

Private university libraries have been taken many initiatives for marketing its products and services such as announcements and discussions in meeting, newsletter, brochures, poster in the library, hand-outs, newspapers, sending personal letter, telephone contract, one to one when the users in the library, one to one discussions in or outside the library, email etc.

The modern library is now generally called an information market and the library user is a consumer of information. Information is a vital resource for research and development of any nation. Marketing is essential in making the proper planning, designing and use of such services and products for the better and optimal use of information. The library should give priority to provide excellent customer service enhancing its image as information provider in the information era. The library and information services should be user (customer) oriented in order to satisfy their information needs effectively. Marketing of library and information services includes customer (users) priorities, expectations, individuality, responsiveness, relationship, quality of services, professional skills and competencies, value-added services, etc. The ultimate aim of marketing here is to provide the right information to the right user at the right time [11].

15. Problems faced by the Library Users

Academic libraries have been described as the 'heart' of learning community; providing a place for students and faculty to conduct education exists to support the goals of its parent organization. Since university libraries are an integral part of higher education system, they should provide support services for the formal educational programs as well as for facilities for research and for generation of new knowledge. In the study we found the following problems which are faced by the users of the non government university library:

1. Collections of the maximum universities are not adequate

2. Subject wise collections are not almost satisfactory. It has been observed that most of the libraries purchased text books according to offered courses. Course-wise reference and supplementary books do not purchase easily.

3. The collections of journal are not enough

4. Most of the libraries do not open individual section for reference books and collections of reference materials are not adequate

5. Most of the libraries are not expert to prepare library service related publications such as Newsletter, Current Awareness Bulletin, Subject Bibliography, Directory, Indexing and Abstracting, Periodical holding list, Union list of serials etc

6. The major problems as the users faced while using the libraries are insufficient reading resources, lack of proper information service and insufficient infrastructural facilities, inconvenient working hours, lack of proper organization of resources, behavior of library staff, lack of adequate cleanliness, insufficient IT facilities etc

7. Lack of insufficient infrastructures and spaces are the major problems of the libraries. Sufficient spaces for the library are not allocated.

8. Most of the libraries are not capable to provide any modern technical facilities for better information services for researches.

9. Library automation is a very useful system for the users. We found that a few of libraries are computerized and most of the libraries are partly computerizes or fully operated manually.

10. Information technology related infrastructures of the libraries are very poor. Only a few of libraries use adequate information technological facilities.

11. It is also found that library networking, resources sharing and inter-library loan services are fully absent of the non government university libraries.

research and extend knowledge. In education system, an academic library is the centre of academic life. A university library or any other library attached to an institution of higher

16. Recommendations for Improving Library Systems and Services

Library is the vital elements for academic life and for educational institutions. So it is very essential to improve the systems and services of the library so this study provides the following suggestions and recommendations for improving library systems and services:

1. Subject wise collections of the libraries should be increased according to the students' demand;

2. Should be collect adequate journal for research purpose;

3. Reference section should be opened with sufficient reference books;

4. Should be published Newsletter, Current Awareness Bulletin, Subject Bibliography, Directory, Indexing and Abstracting, Periodical holding list, Union list of serials, etc;

5. Should be sufficient infrastructural facilities, convenient working hours, proper organization of resources, good behavior of library staff, adequate cleanliness and insufficient IT facilities, etc;

6. Sufficient space for the library should be allocated;
7. Modern technologies should be used and library should be fully automated;
8. Information resources sharing activities should be introduced;
9. Initiatives should be taken for preparing union catalogue.

Conclusion

The history of Private University libraries in Bangladesh are not very old and as compared to the condition of system and services of these libraries and management status are partially structured. Some university libraries are very organized and provide up-to-date information to its users using modern information technology and equipment. A majority of private university libraries in Bangladesh do not have large separate buildings, but they are housed in separate floor. Most private university libraries try to provide enough services through tr libraries.

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